

LASER4SURF

Laser for Mass Production of
functionalised metallic surfaces

D8.4 – Project Website and Social Media Channels

Laser for Mass Production of functionalised metallic surfaces

Contract number:	768636
Project acronym:	LASER4SURF
Project title:	LASER FOR MASS PRODUCTION OF FUNCTIONALISED METALLIC SURFACES

Deliverable number:	D8.4
Dissemination level:	PU (Public)
Report date:	6th February 2018

Author(s):	Barnstedt, Corinna
Partners contributed:	ESCI
Reviewer:	Rodríguez, A.
Contact:	CEIT Paseo de Manuel Lardizábal, nº 15 20018, Donostia-San Sebastián (SPAIN) Phone: +34 943 21 28 00 Email: arodriguez@ceit.es

The LASER4SURF project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 768636

Coordinator: CEIT

DISCLAIMER

The content reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

VERSION CONTROL

Version	Date	Contributors	Sections Affected
1	05 Feb. 2018	Corinna Barnstedt	all
2			

INDEX

1. INTRODUCTION	3
2. THE LASER4SURF PROJECT WEBSITE	4
2.1 Homepage	5
2.2 About LASER4SURF	6
2.3 Laser Technology	6
2.4 Applications	6
2.5 Partners.....	6
2.6 News	6
2.7 Contact and Further Information	6
3. SOCIAL MEDIA	7
3.1 The LASER4SURF LinkedIn Site	7
3.2 The LASER4SURF Twitter Feed	7
3.3 The LASER4SURF YouTube Channel	8

1. INTRODUCTION

The present deliverable is “Public” in nature, i.e. it is not a report. For convenience, we provide a short report below about the structure and the features of the LASER4SURF website and the LASER4SURF social media channels on LinkedIn and Twitter.

The LASER4SURF website is set up along the details of Subtasks 8.2.4 described in work plan table of Annex 1 “Description of the Action” of the Grant Agreement.

2. THE LASER4SURF PROJECT WEBSITE

The overall objective of the dissemination and communication activities is to ensure that the LASER4SURF project website, set up at the very beginning of the project, is the entry point to the LASER4SURF work and achievements for both: the scientific and professional communities and other stakeholders' categories including end users and the general public. It contains all the institutional information about LASER4SURF project. Besides that, the website acts as communication and dissemination channel for the project's results and for the involvement and enlargement of the stakeholders community.

The share point for the LASER4SURF partners containing all institutional information including working documents and deliverables through a reserved partners' area is the team site. This is not part of this deliverable, as it was decided at the Kick-Off Meeting to use the existing private webshare facility of CEIT.

A choice between several options for the domain name of the LASER4SURF website resulted in the following domain: www.laser4surf.eu and www.laser4surf.com. The two domain names have been reserved in November 2017.

The website is managed by ESCI and supervised by CEIT. All partners contribute to the contents of the web site. The technical infrastructure of the site is developed by ANAXIMANDRE, who is also responsible for maintenance, hosting and search engine optimization (SEO). Statistics about visits and visitors of the website will be available in regular intervals.

The navigation within the website is easy and straightforward with pages accessible from the home page and sub pages within the pages. At the current stage of the project, the website will be launched with a light but essential structure that could be enhanced and enlarged as more contents are generated by the project.

The main structure and the main features of the LASER4SURF website are presented in Chapter 2 below and an outlook for further features will be given in Chapter 3.

The technical infrastructure and the graphical interface of the LASER4SURF website was set-up at the very beginning of the project and approved by the consortium. The website is structured in a homepage and three main sections: About LASER4SURF, laser technology and applications.

2.1 Homepage

The main elements of the homepage have been developed in order to give the site visitors a concise and short overview of LASER4SURF project, to enhance the collaboration and interaction among LASER4SURF partners and stakeholders, as well as to facilitate easy access to information.

The homepage provides a link to the LASER4SURF introductory video and two short preview sentences of the About section: “European researchers are exploring how using laser structuring can alter and improve the properties or performance of metals.”

Three use cases will demonstrate how tiny changes in nano dimensions will improve the performance of batteries, linear encoders used in production lines and medical implants.”

Below to the About section, three preview sentences provide information on three application subsections: on “Medical Components”, “Advanced Batteries” and “Linear Encoders”.

Scrolling further down, the reader finds information on the laser technology.

At the bottom of the homepage, information is given on the contact details, recent news, links to the social media channels, links to the partners and a link to legal information on the website.

Figure 1: The LASER4SURF homepage with the dominant video on the top right corner

2.2 About LASER4SURF

The “About” section presents how LASER4SURF is structured as a project. It describes the aims and objectives of LASER4SURF, and how each partner is expected to contribute the work plan that will be implemented as well as the impacts expected from the project.

2.3 Laser Technology

The page on “Laser Technologies” consists of the basic technological principals, used in the project.

2.4 Applications

The section “Applications” contains detailed information about the three LASER4SURF use cases, for which this project will produce processed metal surfaces. This includes a description of the status quo of dental implants, coin cells and batteries for e-mobility and linear encoders as well as the impact the LASER4SURF processing will have on this three particular use cases.

2.5 Partners

On the page “Partners”, each organisation of the LASER4SURF consortium is presented with the logo and a hyperlink to their respective addresses. It is planned to add additional information on the partner’s role in the coming months.

2.6 News

The page “News” is still fairly empty, but as the project progresses, it will include news articles, interviews and press releases in chronological order. They will deal with different aspects of the LASER4SURF technology, prototypes or specific events. ESCI in cooperation with the coordinator and / or project partners will feed the News sections.

2.7 Contact and Further Information

The bottom of the homepage provides additional important information, such as the contact details to the coordinator and media partner, legal information and links to the three social media pages that will be used by LASER4SURF: Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube.

3. SOCIAL MEDIA

3.1 The LASER4SURF LinkedIn Site

Parallel to the launch of the website www.laser4surf.eu, also the LinkedIn Page of LASER4SURF has been launched. It will be a way to connect to the professionals, who are interested in the project, but prefer to follow a LinkedIn group, rather than using Twitter or visiting the website on a regular basis. Figure 2 provides a snapshot of the LASER4SURF LinkedIn page.

Figure 2: LASER4SURF LinkedIn page just after its launch in January 2018

3.2 The LASER4SURF Twitter Feed

During the LASER4SURF Kick-Off Meeting on 17th October 2017, ESCI has set up an LASER4SURF Twitter feed and has started to post the first LASER4SURF news, such as a press release about the Kick-Off Meeting. The partners have already started re-tweeting LASER4SURF news, which has resulted in a steady increase in activity.

Figure 3: The LASER4SURF Twitter Account with currently 9 tweets

3.3 The LASER4SURF YouTube Channel

With the launch of the website, and the introductory video, also the LASER4SURF YouTube Channel was launched. It will provide users and stakeholders to view in one location, all the videos we will produce on the LASER4SURF project, including the introductory video or also short interviews to be used in our LASER4SURF social media campaigns.

Figure 4: The LASER4SURF YouTube Channel